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The roots of culture. The use of *ollae perforatae* in Cagliari (Sardinia, Italy) and the garden as cultural marker of Romanisation.

Ciro Parodo
University of Cagliari

Abstract: A series of ceramic vessels intentionally perforated on the bottom has been found during the archaeological excavation of a rectangular room in via Caprera 8 in Cagliari, in southern Sardinia (Italy), dated to the first half of the 1st century AD. The aim of this paper is to demonstrate their function as *ollae perforatae*, perforated planting pots used in the Roman arboriculture and horticulture practices in order to make a garden, and to analyze their cultural significance in relation to the phenomenon of the so-called 'Romanisation'.

Keywords: Sardinia, *ollae perforatae*, perforated planting pots, garden, Romanisation.

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 Address: University of Cagliari. Department of Humanities, Languages and Cultural Heritage. EIKONIKOS – Laboratorio permanente di Iconografia e Iconologia del Mondo Classico. Piazza Arsenale 1, Cittadella dei Musei - 09124 Cagliari (Italy). Email: ciro.parodo@unica.it

Τῆς παιδείας τὰς μὲν ῥίζας εἶναι πικράς, τὸν δὲ καρπὸν γλυκύν.
The roots of education are bitter, but the fruit is sweet.
(D.L. V, 18, 712)

1. INTRODUCTION. THE ROLE OF THE GARDEN IN THE ROMAN CULTURE

This contribution focuses on the functional analysis of eight perforated ceramic vessels coming from the archeological excavation in the courtyard of 'Agenzia LAORE Sardegna' in via Caprera 8, in Cagliari, south Sardinia (Italy)¹ (fig. 1). The aim is to demonstrate their identification with *ollae perforatae*, perforated planting pots used in the Roman arboriculture and horticulture practices in order to make a garden, and to analyze their cultural meaning in relation to the so-called "Romanisation".

The structure and function of the garden changed considerably during the Roman age². Initially, in the early Middle Republican age, the *horti* of the houses were kitchen gardens and they were used by their owners to grow herbs and vegetables as source of food for their families. According to Plinius the Elder, the ancient *horti* were the symbol of the superior morality of the earlier Romans because «ex horto plebei macellum, quando innocentiore victu»³, «from the garden, a poor man had his marketplace,

¹ The results of this research have been partially anticipated in PARODO 2019a. I would to thank Dr. A.L. Sanna (Soprintendenza Archeologia, Belle Arti e Paesaggio per la città metropolitana di Cagliari e le province di Oristano e Sud Sardegna), responsible of the archaeological excavation in via Caprera 8, Prof. M. Giuman, Prof. R. Martorelli and Prof. C. Del Vais (University of Cagliari, Department of Humanities, Languages and Cultural Heritage), responsible of the related laboratory, and all colleagues who have studied the artefacts coming from the excavation.

² VON STACKELBERG 2009, pp. 9-47; HARTSWICK 2017; MORVILLEZ 2017.

³ Plin. *nat.* 19, 52.

nourishment much more innocent». Later, from the 2nd cent. BC, the gardens associated with the peristyle and decorated with frescoes, mosaics and sculptures became a fundamental vehicle of high social and cultural status, so much that Cicero wrote to Atticus in the ninth *Epistulae ad familiars*: «Si hortum in bibliotheca habes, deerit nihil»⁴, «If you have a garden in the library, you have everything you need».

For this ideological reason, the representation of luxurious *horti* constitutes one of most important figurative theme of upper class mosaic floors, especially in North-Africa, like, for example, the well-known mosaic of *Dominus Iulius* in Carthage (end of the 4th – beginning of the 5th cent. AD), composed of three registers, whose images provide documentary evidence of daily life and wealth of the Roman aristocracy in Late Antiquity⁵ (fig. 2). In the upper register, the wife of the *villa*'s owner, depicted with bracelets on each wrist, sits on a bench among the trees of the garden, while the servants offer her some rural products, like olives, ducks, and lambs. In the lower one the woman, decorated richly dressed in a rose garden, holds a mirror and wears earrings, surrounded by two servants that gift her a basket of flowers and jewelry. On the right side, *Dominus Iulius*, the master of the great estate represented in the center of the mosaic, sits on a chair between two fruit trees of the *hortus* and receives a message that certifies his elite status.

Passing from the utilitarian purpose to the decorative one, and becoming consequently a symbolic medium of self-representation⁶, the

⁴ Cic. *epist.* 9, 4, 1.

⁵ Tunis, Musée National du Bardo. RAECK 1987; NEVETT 2010, pp. 131-141; PARODO 2019b, pp. 8-12.

⁶ PURCELL 1995; VON STACKELBERG 2009, pp. 50-98; MARZANO 2014, pp. 196-203, 230-233.

garden can be considered a remarkable marker of the 'Romanisation'. Sardinia represents a highly interesting area for the study of this debated phenomenon, because its ancient history, marked by the passage from the centuries-old Phoenician-Punic domination to the Roman one, was characterized by the continuity of the Punic traditions and the introduction of new cultural models by Roman-Italic groups⁷.

2. ROMAN SARDINIA AND THE PHENOMENON OF "ROMANISATION"

In the early phase of their domination in Sardinia, the Phoenicians were primarily interested in commercial traffics with local populations, as confirmed by their first permanent settlement, *Sulky*, now Sant'Antioco (SI), founded in the southern coast of the island in the 1st half of the 8th cent. BC with the aim of exploit the mineral resources of this area⁸. The whole south-western Sardinia was involved in a large process of colonization through to the foundation of urban centers with a sea-based economy, in particular fishing and harbor commercial activities, like *Karaly* (now Cagliari), on the center of the homonymous gulf, Nora, near Pula (CA), on the south-west of the same gulf, and Tharros, near Cabras (OR), on the southern border of the Sinis peninsula, in the central-western Sardinia.

The beginning of the Punic conquest of Sardinia, started in the last quarter of the 6th cent. BC, following the guidelines of a more centralized political control, was a moment of decisive socio-economic changes for the island. Carthage, after it has incorporated the ancient Phoenician emporia-

⁷ BERNARDINI 2007; STIGLITZ 2010; ROPPA 2018.

⁸ The bibliography about Phoenician Sardinia is very wide; see particularly: BARTOLONI 2005, pp. 25-43; GUIRGUIS 2017b; ROPPA 2019.

cities, intensified greatly the phenomenon of urbanisation of coastal areas, encouraged the development of settlements in inland areas with a function of military control, and enhanced the exploitation of metallurgical and agricultural resources, in particular the cultivation of cereal crops, in order to integrate the maritime economy of coastal cities with rural resources coming from the hinterland⁹. Due to the crisis caused by the revolt of Carthaginian unpaid mercenaries after the end of the First Punic War, Sardinia was occupied by Rome in 238 BC¹⁰, but its conquest was a gradual process, often hampered by numerous hostile acts, supported by Carthaginians due to their economic interests to the island¹¹, as in particular the guerrilla warfare of the Sardinian landowner Hampsicora in 216-215 BC¹².

However, despite the annexation of the island into the Roman rule as the province *Sardinia et Corsica* in 227 BC¹³, the Punic influence remained notable on many aspects of the Sardinian culture and society until the Late Republican age, as confirmed, for example, by the long-living presence of the Carthaginian administrative institutions, in particular the suffetes, the two annually elected chief magistrates. The best known case is that of suffetes *Aristo* and *Mutumbal* in *Caralis* (42-36 BC), as documented by the issue of coins in bronze with the image of their heads on the obverse and the

⁹ The bibliography about Punic Sardinia is equally wide; see in particular: BARTOLONI 2005, pp. 43-60; ROPPA 2014; BARTOLONI 2017.

¹⁰ Plb. 1, 79-88.

¹¹ MELONI 1990, pp. 43-64; MASTINO 2005b, pp. 65-77; IBBA 2015, pp. 15-19.

¹² Liv. 23, 32, 5; 34, 10; 40, 1; 41, 1; Sil. 12, 342-354, 379-419.

¹³ Str. 17, 3, 25.

depiction of the façade of the Venus temple of *Caralis* on the reverse¹⁴ (fig. 3).

Another example is that of *Himilkat* and *Abdeshmun*, two suffetes mentioned in the trilingual inscription of a votive bronze base made between the 1st half of the 2nd cent. and the 2nd half of the 1st cent. BC, found in San Nicolò Gerrei (SU), written in Latin, Greek and Punic languages¹⁵. It was dedicated by *Cleon*, a servant of oriental origin who worked for a society of *publicani* in *Caralis* involved in the exploitation of the salt pans, in order to thank *Aesculapius-Asclepius-Eshmun Merre* for favours received¹⁶. Due to this large range of the archeological evidence of the Punic culture still in Roman times, Sardinia represents a very interesting case-study for the analysis of Romanisation¹⁷.

Going beyond the Theodor Mommsen's concept of *Romanisierung* as a one-directional process of civilization, elaborated during the 2nd half of the 19th cent., in the last thirty years the analysis of this topic has been at the center of a wide theoretical debate, influenced, from the ideological point of view, by the post-colonial and anti-imperialistic perspectives, in particular in relation to the complex relationships between the Roman Empire and local identities¹⁸. This debate has been focused on the need to reinterpret the

¹⁴ Obverse legend: *ARISTO MUTUMBAL (filius) RICOCE SUF(etes)*; reverse legend: *VENERIS KAR(alis)*. SOLLAI 1989, pp. 51-61; ZUCCA 2004, pp. 86-87; PORRÀ 2007, pp. 54-56.

¹⁵ *CIL* I², 2226 = *CIL* X, 7856 = *ILS* 1874 = *ILLRP* I, 41 = *IG* XIV, 608 = *IGR* I, 511 = *CIS* I, 143. Latin text: *Cleon salari(or)um soc(iorum) s(ervus) Aescolapio Merre donum dedit lubens / merito merente*. Greek text: Ἀσκληπιῶι Μηροῦ ἀνάθεμα βωμὸν ἔστη / σε Κλέων ὁ ἐπὶ τῶν ἀλῶν κατὰ πρόσταγμα. Punic text: To the Lord Eshmun Merre the altar of copper weighing one hundred pounds vowed by Cleon. (Eshmun) has heard his voice and healed him. In the year of the suffetes Himilkat and Abdeshmun, sons of Himilk. ZUCCA 1996, pp. 1463-1465; CULASSO GASTALDI 2000.

¹⁶ ZUCCA 2004, pp. 136-137; MASTINO, ZUCCA 2012, pp. 403-404; IBBA 2016, pp. 76-77.

¹⁷ VAN DOMMELEN 1998; VAN DOMMELEN 2001; VAN DOMMELEN, TERRENATO 2007.

¹⁸ HINGLEY 2005, pp. 14-48; REVELL 2009, pp. 1-39; MATTINGLY 2011, pp. 3-42.

phenomenon of Romanisation, also from a terminological point of view, as a new historiographic category, in order to overcome the obsolete bipolarity between foreign colonizing groups and the native colonized ones¹⁹. Consequently, nowadays Romanisation is identified not simply as a form of acculturation, but as a process of forming of a new cultural system, chronologically and geographically not-homogeneous. For this reason, it has been interpreted in different ways, according to new hermeneutic paradigms and proportionally to the degree of cultural interactions between the Roman component of the society and the native one. As a result, Romanisation has been defined alternatively as ‘hybridisation’²⁰, ‘creolising’/‘pidginisation’²¹ or ‘*métissage*’²², and more recently it has been investigated also on the basis of the modern terms of ‘globalisation’²³ or ‘mondialisation’²⁴ of the Greek-Roman culture.

Being, as many Authors, not convinced of the semantic effectiveness of these solutions due to their political implications²⁵, in this paper I will use the term ‘Romanisation’ in order to define the set of relations between Romans and natives which have created a cross-cultural interactions system in which they attributed reciprocally new meanings and functions to their material and intangible culture, , in accord with to the theories of ‘cultural bricolage’²⁶ and ‘*transferts culturels*’²⁷, though inevitably unbalanced on the

¹⁹ ALFÖLDY 2005; INGLEBERT 2005.

²⁰ VAN DOMMELEN 1997; STOCKHAMMER 2012.

²¹ WEBSTER 2001; CARR 2003.

²² LE ROUX 2004; TRAINA 2006.

²³ VERSLUYS 2014; PITTS, VERSLUYS 2015.

²⁴ VEYNE 2005, pp. 345-377; WALLACE-HADRILL 2008, pp. 3-24.

²⁵ See, among others, LE ROUX 2004, pp. 297-306; CECCONI 2006, pp. 88-92; GALSTERER 2009, pp. 23-27.

²⁶ TERRENATO 1997; ROTH 2007, pp. 19-27.

²⁷ HAACK 2008; LE ROUX 2014.

side of Rome as the winning military power. Particularly in western provinces as Sardinia, where the socio-political structures were less structured than the eastern ones, the elaboration of this process was mediated by a very relevant phenomenon. It is the tendency of the local upper classes, and in the suborder of the lower ones that referred to them, to emulate the cultural models coming from Rome in order to consolidate their primacy within their own community and optimise their relations with the conquerors, on the basis, respectively, of the theoretical models of the 'elite interaction'²⁸ and the 'vulgar Romanisation'²⁹.

3. THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL EXCAVATION OF VIA CAPRERA 8 IN CAGLIARI (SARDINIA) AND THE PERFORATED POTS

The archaeological investigation in the courtyard of 'Agenzia LAORE Sardegna', in via Caprera 8 in Cagliari, made under the direction of the Soprintendenza Archeologia, Belle Arti e Paesaggio per la città metropolitana di Cagliari e le province di Oristano e Sud Sardegna between 2014 and 2015, brought to light a rectangular room (5.20 x 3 m), built between the 3rd and the 1st cent. BC and probably related to a house, with an entrance presumably located in N-E³⁰. From the 2nd half of the 2nd cent. BC, the room underwent a first modification due to the obliteration of the entrance and its internal subdivision, through the building of two

²⁸ MILLET 1990; WOOLF 1997.

²⁹ ALCOCK 2001; MATTINGLY 2002.

³⁰ SANNA 2019, pp. 2-3, 5-6.

partitions, which were demolished when a new floor was also constructed, while the previous wall parameters were preserved³¹.

From the half of the 1st cent. AD, the room was subjected to a landfill action, in order to raise the level of foot traffic and to change its function, because it was probably transformed from internal to external space; immediately later new walls, called USM 44/47 and USM 90/52, were built overlapping the previous ones in direction N-W, while the N side of the room was closed by the wall USM 7/53³². The R1-R8 perforated pots, which are the object of the analysis of this paper, come from the 45 layer (fig. 4).

The first four vessels, from R1 to R4, were aligned along the wall USM 44/47 (fig. 5) and have a hole on the bottom (2.5-3.2 cm diameter). Three of these – R1, R2, R3 – are intact thin-walled little jugs with striped walls of the type Ricci I/30 = Marabini XV = Mayet XXIV form. R1 also has an additional hole in the lower part of the body (fig. 6). R4 was discovered in a fragmentary state and typologically belongs to the pottery production of Sutri (1st form, n. 6)³³. These artefacts were made in central Italy between the end of the 1st cent. BC and the 1st cent. AD, as confirmed by the presence of a coin, hypothetically identifiable with a Late-Republican age uncial reduction³⁴, located between R1 and R2, whose mouth were partially covered by fragments of an amphora wall.

R5 and R6 vessels were placed in front of USM 90/52. The first artefact is a Dressel 2-4 wine amphora coming from the Vesuvian area, dated between the half of the 1st cent. BC and the Julio-Claudian age³⁵. The

³¹ SANNA 2019, pp. 6-8.

³² SANNA 2019, pp. 8-10.

³³ NAPOLITANO 2019, pp. 77-78, 91.

³⁴ D'ORLANDO, MURESU 2019, pp. 583-584.

³⁵ D'ORLANDO 2019, pp. 188, 191-192.

amphora was placed upside down and supported in vertical position by the removed handles, while its upper portion and bottom were resected (fig. 7). It has a *titulus pictus* – P (---) / C (---) E (---) – that could be interpreted hypothetically as the *tria nomina* referring to the producer or trader of amphora; it is interesting to note that the same sequence of letters is attested also for a ceramic vessel from Pompeii containing olives, whose type and origin are unknown³⁶.

R6 is an Italic tradition cooking pot dating back to the Late Republican-Early Augustan ages, whose bottom was not intentionally drilled³⁷, while R7 and R8 vessels, found along the USM 7/53, are two little *ollae* of central Italic production in fragmentary state, which imitate, in larger dimensions, the above-mentioned R1, R2 and R3 thin-walled vessels³⁸.

All R1-R8 vessels were covered with earth when the site was transformed into a landfill between the 2nd half of the 1st cent.-2nd cent. AD, reused between the 4th and the end of the 5th cent., and finally abandoned at the beginning of 6th cent.³⁹

4. THE PERFORATED VESSELS OF VIA CAPRERA: A RITUAL FUNCTION?

Which was the function of these pots? The answer is not immediate. Hypothetically it is possible to suggest their connection with a ritual of foundation which was done in the Etruscan and Roman-Italic world to

³⁶ FARRE 2019, p. 660.

³⁷ PINELLI 2019, pp. 411, 425.

³⁸ PINELLI, PINELLI 2019, pp. 352, 361.

³⁹ SANNA 2019, pp. 10-13.

consecrate the construction of new buildings and monuments, both religious, like temples and altars, and civil ones, like urban walls and doors, under the divine protection⁴⁰. The main elements of this ritual were a bloody or bloodless sacrifice, the deposition of the sacrificial instruments, votive offerings and ceramic containers used for the ceremony into closed deposits, as demonstrated by one of the oldest cases, that of Porta Mugonia in Rome (730-720 BC)⁴¹.

On the contrary, this type of ritual was rarely performed in private buildings: it included the excavation of pits, usually dug under the foundations of the perimeter walls, mosaic floors or plaster of the walls, where the vessels, used for the ceremonial banquet, were placed, often associated with the remains of the sacrifice or other specific objects, in particular coins or nails. An example is the case of Aquileia, where the signs of the foundation ritual have been found in numerous houses, built from the Augustan-Tiberian age to the 6th cent.⁴²

On the basis of this documentation, it should be excluded that the perforated vessels of via Caprera were connected to a foundation ceremony, considering that they were not into closed context of deposition, like pits, and they did not contain any typical ritual element, since the above-mentioned coin has been found outside R1 and R2 pots. At the same time, no organic residue of substances traditionally used in ritual libations, as incense, honey, oil or wine⁴³, has been found inside the perforated pots, as

⁴⁰ D'ALESSIO 2014, pp. 318, 320-324; MICHETTI 2014; PARODO 2018, pp. 108-110.

⁴¹ BONGHI JOVINO 2005, pp. 33-36; LAMBRINOUDAKIS *et alii* 2005, pp. 337-346; BELFIORI 2019, pp. 12-17.

⁴² RIZZO *et alii* 2013, pp. 8-9; FACCHINETTI 2008; FACCHINETTI 2012, pp. 339-344.

⁴³ SIEBERT 1999, pp. 26-59; SCHEID 2005, pp. 189-209, 320-332.

demonstrated by the GC/MS analyses⁴⁴. Furthermore, the fragments of the amphora wall placed above the mouths of R2 and R3 probably did not have a sealing function. Indeed, the presence of the hole at the bottom of all vessels led to the hypothesis that these artefacts are the so-called *ollae perforatae*.

5. THE USE OF *OLLAE PERFORATAE* AND THE PERFORATED VESSELS OF VIA CAPRERA

Although there are numerous denominations, like *calices perforati*⁴⁵ or *vasa fictilia*⁴⁶, that of *ollae perforatae*⁴⁷ is the well-known one and it refers to a particular typology of perforated pots, used in arboriculture and horticulture practices and documented in central Italy, especially in the Vesuvian area, central-southern Britain, *Galliae*, particularly *Belgica* and *Lugdunense*, Greece and the Syro-Palestinian provinces. Generally, they are coarse and small-sized vessels, with a cylindrical or truncated-conical form, a flat bottom, everted rim, without handles, characterized by an accentuated thickness of the walls⁴⁸.

The main characteristic of *ollae perforatae* is the presence of one or more holes greater than 1 cm on the bottom or also on the lower part of the body and, as confirmed by the most important ancient Authors of agronomic

⁴⁴ I would to thank Prof. P.L. Caboni (University of Cagliari, Department of Life and Environmental Sciences) for carrying out the analyzes of R1-R4 perforated vessels by Gas-Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry.

⁴⁵ Cato *agr.* 52; 133.

⁴⁶ Plin. *nat.* 12, 25; 17, 97; 25, 160; Pallad. 3, 25; 4, 10; 6, 6; 10, 14.

⁴⁷ Plin. *nat.* 17, 64.

⁴⁸ MESSINEO 1984; JASHEMSKI 1992b; BARAT, MORIZE 1999, pp. 213-221; MACAULY-LEWIS 2006a.

treatises, like Theophrastus⁴⁹, Cato the Elder⁵⁰, Plinius the Elder⁵¹ and Palladius⁵², these holes were useful to facilitate the drainage of water and the aeration of the roots (fig. 8). The vases were used for sowing fruit and ornamental tree species, for the transport of plants from the nurseries to the gardens where they were planted, and for the propagation by air layering⁵³ (fig. 9). The type of the vegetable crops, in particular flowers, aromatic plants, vines and fruit trees⁵⁴, changed according to their commercial or ornamental function, and depending on the spaces in which the *ollae perforatae* were used, like nurseries, *horti*, sacred and monumental gardens⁵⁵.

Although in the Roman world this typology of vases is documented only from the end of the 1st cent. BC, there are more ancient iconographic evidences, as the *ollae perforatae* depicted on Egyptian frescoes dating back to the beginning of the 15th-14th cent. BC⁵⁶, which would confirm their eastern origin, as written by Theophrastus in his *Historia plantarum*⁵⁷. Especially in the eastern Mediterranean area there are many archaeological evidences about the use of perforated planting pots in sacred and public spaces. The oldest case (3rd cent. BC) is represented by the series of buried *ollae perforatae* surrounding the two long sides of *Hephaisteion* in the Athens Agora in order to make a sacred garden⁵⁸. Another and more recent

⁴⁹ Thphr. *HP* 4, 4, 3; 6, 7, 3

⁵⁰ Cato *agr.* 52; 133.

⁵¹ Plin. *nat.* 12, 25; 17, 97; 17, 64; 25, 160.

⁵² Pallad. 3, 10; 3, 25; 4, 10; 6, 6; 10, 14.

⁵³ JASHEMSKI 1979a, pp. 238-240, 284-285, 293-296; KLYNNE, LILJENSTOLPE 2001, pp. 201-202; JASHEMSKI 2017b, pp. 425-426.

⁵⁴ GLEASON 1994, pp. 17-18; CARROLL 2008, pp. 41-42; JASHEMSKI *et alii* 2017b, pp. 469-470.

⁵⁵ MACAULY-LEWIS 2010, pp. 21-24; CARROLL 2017, pp. 155-162; MACAULY-LEWIS 2017, pp. 99-105, 114-118.

⁵⁶ WILKINSON 1998, p. 76; NICHOLSON, SHAW 2000, p. 139

⁵⁷ Thphr. *HP* 6, 4, 3.

⁵⁸ THOMPSON 1937, pp. 404-425; KOCH 1951, pp. 356-359.

example is the *Tropaeum* built by Octavian between 29 and 27 BC in *Nikopolis* to commemorate the naval victory of Actium (31 BC): this monument was articulated on two superimposed terraces, the upper one surrounded on three sides by a two-nave *stoa*, having an internal garden made with the plants of *ollae perforatae*⁵⁹. Two cases also come from Petra and Jericho, where perforated planting pots were used at the end of the 1st cent. BC in order to decorate respectively the garden with swimming pool⁶⁰, and that one with Ionic peristyle of the winter residence of Herod the Great⁶¹. More specifically, this building provides an interesting example of Romanisation, considering that the king knew so well the Roman traditions that he replaced them in the Judean city⁶².

While in the eastern Mediterranean area the *ollae perforatae* were mainly used to build monumental gardens, in the western regions of the Roman Empire their use is more frequent in private spaces, also for commercial purposes such as the Garden of Hercules in Pompeii (II, 8, 6)⁶³, in particular in *domus* and *villae* of central Italy, both in very high-ranking and lower social level houses. With regard to the first case, it is emblematic the example of the *villa* of Livia at Prima Porta (Rome), whose peristyle, built in the last quarter of the 1st cent. BC, housed a garden made with perforated planting pots, aligned along the colonnade and in the intercolumns⁶⁴. Concerning the second case, the archaeological evidences are more numerous, coming in particular from Pompeii, and all are dated between

⁵⁹ MURRAY, PETSAS 1989, p. 85; ZACHOS 2003, p. 81.

⁶⁰ MACAULY-LEWIS 2006B, pp. 159-164; BEDAL *et alii* 2007, pp. 313-315, 323-326.

⁶¹ GLEASON 1993, pp. 159-161; BEDAL 2004, pp. 171-178.

⁶² EVYSAF 2006, p. 198; MACAULY-LEWIS 2017, pp. 118-120.

⁶³ JASHEMSKI 1979b, pp. 408-410; JASHEMSKI 2017a, pp. 143-144.

⁶⁴ LILJESTOLPE, KLYNNE 2000, pp. 223-225; KLYNNE, LILJENSTOLPE 2001, pp. 201-203.

the 1st cent. BC and 79 AD, such as, for example, the House of *Caius Iulius Polybius* (IX, 13, 1-3), where the garden was composed of trees and vineyard planted with *ollae perforatae*⁶⁵, and, above all, that of *Marcus Fabius Rufus* (VII, 16, 22).

Here, the archaeological excavation, conducted by the University 'Suor Orsola Benincasa' of Napoli from 2004 in a large garden (1581 m²) located in the western area of the *domus*, brought to light numerous perforated planting pots⁶⁶. Between the end of the 1st cent. BC and the 1st half of the 1st cent. AD, five cisterns for the collection of rainwater were built in this area, later dismantled in order to build a portico, damaged by the earthquake of 62 CE. Subsequently, the space was used as a landfill to dispose the building materials used in the restoration of the damaged house, and then as a *hortus* made with the *ollae perforatae*⁶⁷. The specific arrangement of these vessels and their use in an space that changed its intended use during the time, provides a highly interesting comparison for the functional interpretation of the perforated pots of via Caprera (fig. 10).

The various typologies of the vessels from Cagliari, having several and specific sizes, were probably chosen according to the different types of plants which they had to contain, like the *ollae perforatae* of *villa* of Livia at Prima Porta⁶⁸, and those of the *Heliogabalium* garden (221 AD) at Vigna Barberini⁶⁹ (fig. 11), so that jugs (R1, R2, R3) and *ollae* (R7, R8) of via Caprera could have been used to plant minute flower bushes, while the amphora

⁶⁵ JASHEMSKI 1992a, p. 98; JASHEMSKI 1992b, p. 278.

⁶⁶ GRIMALDI *et alii* 2011, pp. 1-6; GRIMALDI *et alii* 2011-2012, pp. 127-136.

⁶⁷ GRIMALDI *et alii* 2010, pp. 1-3; GRIMALDI *et alii* 2011, pp. 9-10.

⁶⁸ MACAULY-LEWIS 2006b, p. 216; PINTO-GUILLAUME 2008, pp. 5-7.

⁶⁹ TOMEI 1992, pp. 942-943; RIZZO 2018, pp. 473-474.

(R5) and the cooking pot (R6) to plant more voluminous shrubs⁷⁰. The use of amphorae with the buried neck and the perforated bottom was widespread in the Roman arboricultural practice, as confirmed by the gardens of the *villa* of Poppea in Oplontis (1st cent. AD)⁷¹, the Temple of Peace in Rome (75 AD)⁷², and the above-mentioned temple dedicated by the emperor Elagabalus to *Sol Elagabalus* (fig. 12).

The same alignment of the perforated vases around the wall perimeter of the room of via Caprera could confirm their use in an ornamental garden, according to a type of arrangement already documented by other cases, such as those of the *villae* of Poppea and San Marco in Stabia (Augustan-Claudian age)⁷³. The presence of hedgehog spines and malacological findings in the earth conserved inside R1, R2, R3 and R4 pots would represent a further confirmation of their use as *ollae perforatae*, because similar remains, found also into other perforated planting pots, like those of temple of Venus in Pompeii (VIII, 1) (end of the 2nd cent. AD) and of *villa* of Livia at Prima Porta, provide very important sources of carbonate used as fertilizer and anti-weed⁷⁴.

6. CONCLUSIONS. THE POSSIBLE EXISTENCE OF A GARDEN IN VIA CAPRERA AND THE PROCESS OF ROMANISATION OF CAGLIARI

⁷⁰ CARROLL 2008, p. 42; GLEASON, PALMER 2017, p. 375.

⁷¹ BARAT, MORIZE 1999, pp. 215, 221; GLEASON 2014, pp. 1017, 1033.

⁷² CARROLL 2017, pp. 157-158; JASHEMSKI *et alii* 2017b, pp. 444-445.

⁷³ MACAULY-LEWIS 2006b, pp. 213-214; GLEASON, PALMER 2017, pp. 380-384.

⁷⁴ PINTO-GUILLAUME 2002, p. 54; CARROLL 2008, p. 40; VICO *et alii* 2007, p. 208.

The hypothetical identification of the perforated vases of via Caprera with *ollae perforatae* can be supported by the consideration that the area of *Caralis* in which they have been discovered was a residential one, and characterized by an intense infrastructural process during the Roman age, as documented by the discovery of numerous hydraulic devices⁷⁵. The residential character of this area, concentrated around via Caprera and viale Trieste, is confirmed both by its morphological characteristics, and some archeological evidence. One of these is the *domus* in viale Trieste 105, divided into several rooms, some with mosaic floors, used from the 3rd-2nd cent. BC until the 6th cent. AD, as well as the thermal building near via Caprera, dating back to the 2nd half of the 2nd cent. AD⁷⁶, adorned by valuable sculptures, among which an acephalous statue of *Venus Pudica* and two statues of Bacchus with panther⁷⁷.

The existence of a garden in *Caralis* can be analyzed from two perspectives. First, in the light of the urbanisation process of the city⁷⁸, one of the most efficacious element of Romanisation, especially in western provinces like North-African and Iberian ones⁷⁹, although in Sardinia it was strongly chronologically and geographically discontinuous⁸⁰. The second

⁷⁵ COLAVITTI 2003, p. 75; GHIOTTO 2005, p. 183; PIETRA 2019b, p. 158.

⁷⁶ MONGIU 1986, pp. 133-135, 139; MARTORELLI 2009, pp. 218-219; GIUMAN, MARTORELLI 2019, pp. 718-722.

⁷⁷ Cagliari, Museo Archeologico Nazionale. ANGIOLILLO 1987, p. 151; ANGIOLILLO 1989, pp. 206-207.

⁷⁸ GHIOTTO 2005, pp. 180-183; ROPPA 2013, pp. 47-53; DE VINCENZO 2016, pp. 123-127.

⁷⁹ FEAR 1996, pp. 6-30; CHERRY 1998, pp. 75-97; REVELL 2009, pp. 40-78.

⁸⁰ DYSON 2000; ROPPA 2013, pp. 135-138; a more recent analysis of this topic was made by C. Parodo and D. D'Orlando in a lecture entitled "Urbanisation in Roman Sardinia from the 3rd to the 1st cent. BC" presented on the occasion of the Conference "Diverging Trajectories: Urbanism and the Roman conquest of Italy" (KNIR - Royal Netherlands Institute in Rome, Rome, 27-28 June 2018), under the scientific direction of F. Colivicchi, M. McCallum and T.D. Stek, which is going to be published in the proceedings of the conference.

important point of view is the presence in the city of human groups coming from central Italy, the area of peninsula with the highest evidence of *ollae perforatae*, as the same perforated planting pots from via Caprera confirm.

As testified by one of the clauses of the Punic-Roman treaty, signed in 348 BC, which prohibited Romans to promote commercial relations in Sardinia and to found colonies⁸¹, the great economic potential of the island attracted the members of the central Italic middle class, especially businessmen (*negotiatores* and *mercatores*) and public contractors (*publicani*)⁸². The impact of their presence in Sardinia was extremely relevant from a cultural point of view, as documented more specifically by three monuments in *Caralis*, which become *oppidum civium Romanorum* supposedly thanks to the intervention of Octavian in 38-36 BC after the war against Sextus Pompey⁸³.

Following a chronological order, the first example is the temple originally situated in via Malta, near Piazza del Carmine, in Cagliari and dedicated to Venus, built between the 2nd half and the end of the 2nd cent. BC. On the basis of its planimetric and architectural characteristics, the shrine was built like the Central Italic typological model of the terraced sanctuary, like those of *Iuno Gabina* in Gabii and *Hercules Victor* in Tivoli (mid 2nd cent. BC)⁸⁴. It was a tetrastyle temple on podium, probably delimited by a *triporticus*, which was in axis with a theatrical *cavea*, supposedly for celebration of the *ludi scaenici* in honor of Adonis, divine

⁸¹ Plb. 3, 24, 3-11.

⁸² MELONI 1990, pp. 112-115; COLAVITTI 1999, pp. 39-46; ANGIOLILLO 2013.

⁸³ Plin. *nat.* 3, 7, 85. About this controversial topic see: PORRÀ 2007, pp. 62-63; IBBA 2017, pp. 186-187.

⁸⁴ COARELLI 1987, pp. 11-21; 85-112; D'ALESSIO 2011.

partner of Venus⁸⁵ (fig. 13). The same presence of the high podium of Italic tradition, a rare element in the sacred architecture of the Roman Sardinia, and a notable marker of the Romanisation of the island, testifies also a political purpose⁸⁶. It is known that there exists a significant connection between the Roman expansionism and the architectural type of the terraced sanctuary, which represents a symbol of the new juridical status achieved in the territories conquered by the Romans, as demonstrated by the sanctuary of Munigua, in southern Spain, in ancient *Baetica*, built during the reign of Vespasian following the achievement of the *ius Latii* by the civic community⁸⁷.

The second example is a funerary monument with Doric frieze, belonging to one of the two types of Hellenistic monuments characterized by the presence of *dado* or *ara* which were widespread in central Italy between the Late Republican Age and the Early Augustan Age⁸⁸. The monument found in via XX Settembre in Cagliari and dated to the 1st cent. BC, is adorned by a metopal decoration consisting of six-petal flowers and umbilicated *paterae*, and its patron, as confirmed by the inscription⁸⁹, was the Etruscan *Caius Apsena Pollio*⁹⁰ (fig. 14). It is possible that also the patron of the *fullonica* in the same street, *Marcus Plotius Rufus*, was a Middle Italic businessman, as confirmed not only by the onomastic analysis of his name⁹¹,

⁸⁵ ANGIOLILLO 1986-1987; BONETTO 2006, pp. 261-266; TOMEI 2008, pp. 79-99, 212-213.

⁸⁶ GHIOTTO 2005, pp. 53-54; PIETRA 2019a, pp. 73-74.

⁸⁷ STEK 2014; STEK 2017.

⁸⁸ TORELLI 1995, pp. 159-189; POLITO 2010.

⁸⁹ C. APSENA C. F. HEIC / HEIC EST POLLIO (AE 1986, 271). SOTGIU 1988, pp. 635-636; ZUCCA 1996, pp. 1460-1461).

⁹⁰ ANGIOLILLO 1985, pp. 99-102; BONETTO 2006, p. 267; PARODO 2017, pp. 119-120.

⁹¹ M(ARCUS) PLOTI(US) SILISONIS F(ILIUS) RUFUS (ILSard I, 58). SOTGIU 1988, pp. 561, 629; ZUCCA 1996, pp. 1459-1460).

but also by the style of the mosaic, dated to the 1st cent. BC. Indeed the third example is the mosaic which decorates the ancient laundry; it is characterized by typical motifs of Hellenistic art, widespread in Italic area, like flowers with six spindle-shaped petals, dolphins in association with anchors, rudders and double axes⁹² (fig. 15).

In conclusion, the existence of a private *hortus* in *Caralis* related with an owner coming from central Italy is plausible in the light of the dynamics of the cultural Romanisation involving Sardinia. From this point of view, an interesting comparison with the case of via Caprera comes from a Late Republican *domus* in via Falzarego, near viale Sant'Avendrace, on the slopes of the Tuvixeddu hill in the north-western Cagliari, the main funerary area of the Punic city⁹³. Here, in 1940, the remains of a possible *hortus* were discovered, made with fifty-four amphorae, cut in half and buried side by side⁹⁴ (fig. 16). The *domus* is composed of six rooms, whose three have been hypothetically identified with the *tablinum* and the *alae* of the typical Roman house plan⁹⁵. The presence of this *domus* and other ones, like the coeval "Casa degli emblemata punici" ("The House of the Punic emblems")⁹⁶, as well as cisterns, confirms the partial change of the previous funerary function of this area⁹⁷. This is probably related to the repositioning of *Caralis* in the Roman age, when the area of Piazza del Carmine become the center of the city, as demonstrated by the presence of the *forum*, with some of the main

⁹² ANGIOLILLO 1981, pp. 85-86; ANGIOLILLO 2013, pp. 22, 27-28; Angiolillo 2017, p. 127

⁹³ The bibliography about the necropolis of Tuvixeddu is very wide; see more recently; STIGLITZ 2007, pp. 58-60; STIGLITZ 2014, pp. 130-131.

⁹⁴ PUGLISI 1943, pp. 157-160; SALVI 2000, pp. 160-161; COLAVITTI 2003, pp. 24-25.

⁹⁵ For a discussion about the plan of the house of via Falzarego see: GHIOTTO 2005, p. 162; ROPPA 2013, pp. 48-49.

⁹⁶ ANGIOLILLO 1981, pp. 105-106; TRONCHETTI 1990, pp. 13-14.

⁹⁷ STIGLITZ 1999, pp. 18-19, 22; COLAVITTI 2003, pp. 85-86; STIGLITZ 2014, pp. 132-133.

civil buildings, like the *tribunal*, the *tabularium* and the *praetorium*, and the *capitolium*⁹⁸, other meaningful elements of Romanisation process⁹⁹.

⁹⁸ GHIOTTO 2005, p. 181; ROPPA 2013, p. 51; DE VINCENZO 2016, p. 125.

⁹⁹ STEK 2015, pp. 7-8, 16 25-28; STEK 2016, pp. 296-298.

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Fig. 1. Map of Cagliari (from GHIOTTO 2005, fig. 86 & <http://d-maps.com>; figure elaborated by C. Parodo).

Fig. 1. Mosaic of *Dominus Iulius* (Tunis, Musée National du Bardo; courtesy of M. Khanoussi).

Fig. 3. Coin of suffetes *Aristo* and *Mutumbal* in *Caralis* (from BONETTO 2006, fig. 8; picture elaborated by C. Parodo).

Fig. 4. Drawing of the archaeological excavation of via Caprera (from SANNA 2019, tav. II).

Fig. 5. R1-R4 perforated pots aligned along the wall USM 44/47 (photo courtesy of A.L. Sanna).

Fig. 6. R1, R2, R3 perforated thin-walled vases (from PARODO 2019a, figs. 2b, 2c, 3a, 3b, 4a, 4b; pictures by M. Todde & D. D'Orlando; picture elaborated by C. Parodo).

Fig. 7. R5 perforated Dressel 2-4 amphora (picture by M. Todde & D. D'Orlando) from the archaeological excavation of via Caprera (picture by A.L. Sanna) (picture elaborated by C. Parodo).

Fig. 8. Example of *olla perforata* from the House of Ship Europa, Pompeii (I, 15) (from JASHEMSKI 2017b, fig. 16.11).

Fig. 9. Example of *olla perforata* from the *villa* of Poppea, Oplontis (from GLEASON 2014, fig. 6.24).

Fig. 10. *Ollae perforatae* from the archeological excavation of the House of *Marcus Fabius Rufus*, Pompeii (VII, 16, 22) (from GRIMALDI *et alii* 2010, fig. 3) and those from via Caprera (photo courtesy of A.L. Sanna; picture elaborated by C. Parodo).

Fig. 11. Reconstruction of part of the *Heliogabalium* garden (from JASHEMSKI 2017b, fig. 16.9a) (figure elaborated by C. Parodo).

Fig. 12. Amphorae reused as planting pots (without scale in the original picture from RIZZO 2018, fig. 9) from the archeological excavation of the *Heliogabulum*, Rome (from TOMEI 1992, fig. 18 (picture elaborated by C. Parodo)).

Fig. 13. Plan of Venus temple in Cagliari (n. 6), and those of the main terraced sanctuaries in central Italy (from D'ALESSIO 2011, fig. 5; figure elaborated by C. Parodo).

Fig. 14. The funerary monument with Doric frieze of *Caius Apsena Pollio* in Cagliari (from ANGIOLILLO 2013: fig. 37).

Fig. 15. Mosaic of *Marcus Plotius Rufus* from the *fullonica* in via XX Settembre, Cagliari (from ANGIOLILLO 2017: p. 128).

Fig. 16. Roman *domus* of via Falzarego (Cagliari) (from PUGLISI 1943, fig. 1).